

A NONLOCAL CONTINUUM DAMAGE MODEL FOR BRITTLE FRACTURE

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to develop a nonlocal continuum damage model for brittle fracture. The present model is developed based on a recently developed “local” model, with an integral-type regularization technique, so that it can rigorously handle damage anisotropy, distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior, and damage deactivation. The “local” damage conjugate force tensor is regularized to yield a nonlocal one, and the thermodynamic equations are formulated in a nonlocally generalized standard manner. A fully explicit integration scheme for the present model is developed. The present model is validated through calibrating its associated material parameters via single edge notched bend tests on concrete beams. It is found to be capable of producing realistic fracture paths, and capturing size effects in real materials. A wide variety of mechanical behavior can be incorporated into the present model in the future.

1. INTRODUCTION

Microscopic defects, such as microcracks and microvoids, are inevitable in real materials. The initiation, growth, and coalescence of microscopic defects often cause material degradation, loss of structural integrity (or durability), or even catastrophic failure and should be traced or avoided. Continuum damage mechanics (CDM) is concerned with the modeling of various damage behavior of various materials. Despite the development of CDM, locally-defined continuum damage models often encounter difficulties when implemented in finite element codes for fracture prediction. This is because: 1. a real material often has a characteristic length of heterogeneity (e.g., the maximum aggregate size in concrete [5]), but a “local” continuum damage model assumes a material to be homogeneous at any length scales; 2. such a model often produces localized local (displacement, stress, and strain) fields and highly mesh-dependent fracture paths in the presence of strain softening [3]. Therefore, there is a need for a “nonlocal” continuum damage model capable of producing realistic, mesh-independent local fields and fracture paths.

A continuum damage model is mostly developed based on a thermodynamic framework. The laws of thermodynamics describe how the state variables selected for a thermodynamic system behave under various conditions. A damage factor/tensor measures damages within a material and is often selected as the damage state variable (see Betten [8] for more details). The strain tensor, the damage tensor, and the damage accumulation state variable(s) form a complete set of state variables for a damageable material. Among various continuum damage models, generalized standard models have been attracting considerable attention for decades because they possess many advantageous features (see Halphen and Nguyen [21] and Hackl [20]

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for more details). Elaborate efforts have been devoted to developing rigorous and versatile “local” continuum damage models. Specifically, brittle damage behavior includes but is not limited to:

1. damage anisotropy—a material is vulnerable to damage in some directions but resistant to damage in some others, due to certain texture patterns or certain external loads;
2. distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior—a material is vulnerable to damage in tension but resistant to damage in compression, due to different damage mechanisms;
3. damage deactivation—during cyclic loading, some preexisting microcracks opening up (or active) in tension close up (or become inactive) in compression and less or negligibly degrade the material.

Faria et al. [19] and Wu et al. [35] modeled damage isotropy and distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior simultaneously, and several others [15, 33, 34, 1] took damage anisotropy into account. Despite improvements, all these authors neglected possible links between tensile and compressive damages. Damage deactivation often causes a material to undergo a sudden increase in its stiffness when loading switches from tension to compression. Ladevèze and Lemaitre [23] successfully modeled damage isotropy and damage deactivation simultaneously. Ramtani [30] and Ju [22] later took damage anisotropy into account by assuming that the elastic potential energy could be decomposed into its tensile and compressive parts, where a tensile/compressive part was a function of tensile/compressive stresses only. Chaboche [11] proved that this decomposition omitted some crossed terms being functions of both tensile and compressive stresses and introduced thermodynamic inconsistency. Chaboche and his coworkers [11, 12, 13, 14] developed a class of thermodynamically consistent constitutive models capable of handling damage anisotropy and damage deactivation simultaneously, without retorting to the above decomposition, and achieved a series of good predictions. Recently Zhang and Yu [37] developed a continuum damage model capable of rigorously handling damage anisotropy, distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior, and damage deactivation. Despite success, there is a critical need for developing a nonlocal continuum damage model based on this “local” model.

With a so-call regularization technique, a nonlocal continuum damage model can be developed based on a “local” model. A regularization technique involves replacing one (or more) locally defined state variable with a corresponding nonlocally regularized state variable. An extensive review of early nonlocal models can be found in Bažant and Jirásek [4]. Recently developed nonlocal models can be classified into two groups, according to their regularization techniques:

1. integral-type—a nonlocal variable is a spatially weighted integral of its corresponding local variable over the neighborhood of a damaged material point [28, 10, 9, 16, 25];
2. gradient-enhanced—a nonlocal variable is related to its corresponding local variable via a nonhomogeneous Poisson/Helmholtz equation [27, 18, 2, 29].

Gradient-enhanced models are derived from integral-type models. Peerlings et al. [27] expanded a local variable to be regularized into a Taylor series in the neighborhood of a damaged material point, substituted the expression for a nonlocal variable in an integral-type model into the Taylor series, and firstly achieved an aforementioned Poisson/Helmholtz equation. Although integral-type and gradient-enhanced models have their respective advantages and drawbacks, integral-type models, as nonlocal models in their original forms, are more general. In this paper, focus is placed on integral-type models to seek generality.

Different chosen options on the local variables to be regularized also lead to different nonlocal models. One option is to regularize the strain tensor [27, 18, 29]. This option, however, contradicts the principle of maximum dissipation. The resulting non-generalized standard models hereby do not possess the advantageous features of generalized standard models. Other options include regularizing: 1. the damage factor/tensor [2]; 2. the damage conjugate force (tensor) [28]; 3. both [10, 9, 16]. The principle of maximum dissipation suggests that the damage conjugate force (tensor) is one controlling factor of damage evolution. The latter

two options turn out to be more favorable. In fact, the second option has the following advantages over the third option, due to its simplicity: 1. it facilitates the model development; 2. it endows a model with better convergence. In this paper, the damage conjugate force tensor is chosen as the local variable to be regularized. Despite the development of integral-type models:

1. most existing models assume damage isotropy, and there is a need for a generalized standard model capable of handling realistic brittle damage behavior, especially damage anisotropy;
2. although explicit finite element analyzers are widely used to simulate damage and fracture, there is not a fully explicit integration scheme for integral-type models.

In summary, there is a critical need for overcoming these shortcomings.

The objective of this paper is to develop a nonlocal continuum damage model for brittle fracture. The present model is developed based on a recently developed "local" model, with an integral-type regularization technique, so that it can rigorously handle damage anisotropy, distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior, and damage deactivation. The "local" damage conjugate force tensor is regularized to yield a nonlocal one, and the thermodynamic equations are formulated in a nonlocally generalized standard manner. A fully explicit integration scheme for the present model is developed. The present model is validated through calibrating its associated material parameters via single edge notched bend (SENB) tests on concrete beams.

2. THERMODYNAMICS AND ENERGY EQUIVALENCE

Let ψ denote the Helmholtz free energy per unit mass of a material. It can be treated as a function of a suitable set of independent state variables describing the elasticity and damage of the material, e.g.,

$$\psi = \psi(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \mathbf{d}, \beta), \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ denotes the elastic strain tensor, \mathbf{d} is a symmetric second-order tensor measuring damages, namely the second-order damage tensor, and β is a scalar describing damage accumulation, respectively. Assume that ψ can be decomposed into its elastic and damage accumulation parts, i.e.,

$$\psi(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \mathbf{d}, \beta) = \psi_e(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \mathbf{d}) + \psi_d(\beta). \quad (2)$$

The thermodynamic driving forces conjugate to the state variables in Eq. (2) are defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \rho \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = \rho \frac{\partial \psi_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}}, \quad \mathbf{y} = -\rho \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \mathbf{d}} = -\rho \frac{\partial \psi_e}{\partial \mathbf{d}}, \quad B = \rho \frac{d\psi}{d\beta} = \rho \frac{d\psi_d}{d\beta}, \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ denotes the stress tensor, \mathbf{y} denotes the damage conjugate force tensor, and B is related to the current damage threshold.

For isothermal deformation, the Clausius–Duhem inequality can be written as

$$\Phi = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} - \rho \dot{\psi} \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

where Φ denotes the dissipation per unit volume, and the overdot denotes the time derivative of a quantity. Combining Eqs. (2)–(4) gives

$$\Phi = \mathbf{y} : \dot{\mathbf{d}} - B \dot{\beta} \geq 0. \quad (5)$$

Let Ω denote the domain occupied by the material (with boundary $\partial\Omega$), and let $\langle \cdot \rangle = \int_{\Omega} (\cdot) dV$ denote the volume integral of a quantity over Ω . Define nonlocal damage conjugate force tensor $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ as

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}} = \int_{\Omega} \bar{w}(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\xi}) \mathbf{y}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{w} = w/\langle w \rangle$ is a normalized weight function with

$$w(\mathbf{x}) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{x}\|^2}{l_c^2}\right) \quad (7)$$

and l_c being the characteristic length of heterogeneity. Also define nonlocal damage dissipation

$$\bar{\Phi} = \bar{\mathbf{y}} : \dot{\mathbf{d}} - B\dot{\beta}. \quad (8)$$

Let f denote the nonlocal damage function. Following Simo and Hughes [31], assume that the following principle of maximum nonlocal dissipation applies throughout this paper: for fixed but otherwise arbitrary $\dot{\mathbf{d}}$ and $\dot{\beta}$, the actual $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ and B should maximize $\bar{\Phi}$ subject to constraint $f \leq 0$, or mathematically speaking, should maximize Lagrange functional

$$L(\bar{\mathbf{y}}, B, \lambda; \dot{\mathbf{d}}, \dot{\beta}) = \bar{\mathbf{y}} : \dot{\mathbf{d}} - B\dot{\beta} - \lambda f, \quad (9)$$

where λ is a positive Lagrange multiplier. This is the equivalent of solving associated damage evolution laws

$$\dot{\mathbf{d}} = \lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \bar{\mathbf{y}}} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{\beta} = \lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial B} \quad (10)$$

subject to Kuhn–Tucker conditions, or loading/unloading conditions,

$$f \leq 0, \quad \lambda \geq 0, \quad \lambda f = 0, \quad (11)$$

which physically mean that damage evolution is irreversible. Eq. (10) implies that f must be a function of $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ and B .

In CDM, researchers introduced the concepts of effective space and energy equivalence to facilitate the derivation of constitutive relations. The effective space is where a fictitious, undamaged material is obtained from a real, damaged one by removing all damage so that a set of so-called effective quantities can be defined to facilitate the derivation. The energy equivalence hypothesis [17] specifies the correspondence between effective quantities and quantities measurable in the real space, namely apparent quantities. It follows the definition of the effective stress tensor: the effective stress tensor should be applied to an undamaged material element such that it produces the same elastic Helmholtz free energy and plastic dissipation as those observed on a damaged material element subject to the apparent stress tensor [6], i.e.,

$$\rho\psi_e = \frac{1}{2}\boldsymbol{\epsilon} : \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \frac{1}{2}\tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} : \tilde{\mathbf{C}} : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}, \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{C} denotes the apparent elasticity tensor, and the overtilde denotes an effective quantity (e.g., $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ denotes the effective or the initial elasticity tensor, which remains constant during continued deformation). Following Betten [7], let $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ be related to $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ by

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathcal{M} : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad \text{or} \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \quad (13)$$

where \mathcal{M} denotes the fourth-order damage effect tensor. Following Zhang and Yu [37], let

$$\mathcal{D} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 d_{ij} \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_j \otimes \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_j \quad (14)$$

denote a fourth-order diagonal damage tensor, where \mathbf{e}_i denotes the unit vector. Let \mathcal{M}^{-1} be related to \mathcal{D} by

$$\mathcal{M}^{-1} = \mathcal{I} - \mathcal{D}, \quad (15)$$

where \mathcal{I} denotes the fourth-order identity tensor. Hooke's law can be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \tilde{\mathbf{C}} : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \quad (16)$$

in the apparent and the effective spaces, respectively. Combining Eqs. (12), (13), and (16) gives

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \quad \text{or} \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathcal{M} : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}. \quad (17)$$

Substituting Eq. (17) into Eq. (12) gives

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathbf{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1}. \quad (18)$$

3. DAMAGE MODEL

In this paper, nonlocality is introduced so that the damage model can be developed similarly to those in a "local" continuum damage model. In this section, the damage model will be developed following Zhang and

Yu [37]. One major difference between the present model and the one in Zhang and Yu [37] is that here $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ rather than \mathbf{y} is the controlling factor of damage evolution. More details on some derivation in this section can be found in Zhang and Yu [37].

Suppose that the material exhibits damage anisotropy, distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior, and damage deactivation. It is beneficial to first specify all damage parameters to be calibrated via a series of tension/compression and pure shear tests. Assume that the material obeys damage criterion

$$f^\pm(\bar{\mathbf{y}}, B^\pm) = (1 - \chi) \|\bar{\mathbf{y}}\|_{\mathcal{J}^\pm} + \chi \mathbf{j}^\pm : \bar{\mathbf{y}} - k^\pm - B^\pm \leq 0 \quad (19)$$

in entire tension/compression, where the superscript +/- denotes a parameter measured via tension/compression tests unless otherwise specified,

$$\|\bar{\mathbf{y}}\|_{\mathcal{J}^\pm} = \sqrt{\bar{\mathbf{y}} : \mathcal{J}^\pm : \bar{\mathbf{y}}} \quad (20)$$

with \mathcal{J}^\pm being a fourth-order tensor describing damage anisotropy, k^\pm denotes the initial damage threshold, $0 \leq \chi \leq 1$ denotes a parameter describing the curvature of the damage surface, and \mathbf{j}^\pm is a second-order tensor also describing damage anisotropy. Let \mathcal{J}^\pm be related to \mathbf{j}^\pm by

$$\mathcal{J}_{iiii}^\pm = (j_{ii}^\pm)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}_{ijij}^\pm = 2(j_{ij}^\pm)^2 \quad (i \neq j, \text{ and no summation over } i \text{ or } j) \quad (21)$$

(the other components of \mathcal{J}^\pm vanish), and set $j_{11}^\pm = 1$ and $\mathcal{J}_{1111}^\pm = 1$. Eqs. (2) and (3) imply that B is a function of β , i.e., $B = B(\beta)$, which is referred to as the damage accumulation law, whose form varies from case to case. Assume that the damage accumulation law takes the form of $B^\pm = B^\pm(\beta)$ in entire tension/compression, whose specific form is to be determined. Note that, given uniform stress and strain fields, a nonlocal continuum damage model is equivalent to a ‘‘local’’ one. Therefore, the above damage parameters can be calibrated via tension/compression and pure shear tests, similarly to Zhang and Yu [37].

The basic idea of modeling distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior is to treat tensile and compressive stresses as another cause of damage anisotropy, just like texture patterns and external loads, and to treat distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior as another consequence of damage anisotropy. With this idea, one can properly define the parameters describing damage anisotropy to produce distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior. Specifically, $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ can be expressed as

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \tilde{\sigma}_i \mathbf{p}_i \otimes \mathbf{p}_i, \quad (22)$$

where \mathbf{p}_i denotes its i th principal unit vector, and $\tilde{\sigma}_i = \mathbf{p}_i \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_i$ denotes its i th eigenvalue. Following Ortiz [26], define two fourth-order projection tensors

$$\mathcal{P}^- = \sum_{i=1}^3 \tilde{H}(-\tilde{\sigma}_i) \mathbf{p}_i \otimes \mathbf{p}_i \otimes \mathbf{p}_i \otimes \mathbf{p}_i \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{P}^+ = \mathcal{I} - \mathcal{P}^- \quad (23)$$

so that \mathcal{P}^\pm can project a second-order tensor onto the tensile/compressive part of $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, say $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^\pm$, i.e.,

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^\pm = \mathcal{P}^\pm : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\tilde{H}(\tilde{\sigma}_i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \tilde{\sigma}_i < 0, \\ H(\tilde{\sigma}_m) & \tilde{\sigma}_i = 0, \\ 1 & \tilde{\sigma}_i > 0 \end{cases} \quad \text{with} \quad H(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x < 0, \\ 1 & x \geq 0. \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

In Eq. (25), $H(x)$ denotes the Heaviside step function, and $\tilde{\sigma}_m$ denotes the mean effective stress. $\tilde{H}(\tilde{\sigma}_i)$ is defined so that damages are entirely tensile/compressive in uniaxial/biaxial tension/compression. Let $\zeta = k^+/k^-$ be a parameter describing the contrast between tensile and compressive damage behavior. Assume that the material obeys damage criterion

$$f(\bar{\mathbf{y}}, B) = \bar{\mathbf{y}}_{eq} - k - B \leq 0 \quad (26)$$

regardless of loading, where

$$\bar{y}_{eq} = (1 - \chi) \sqrt{\bar{y} : \mathcal{J} : \bar{y}} + \chi \mathbf{j} : \bar{y} \equiv (1 - \chi) \|\bar{y}\|_{\mathcal{J}} + \chi \mathbf{j} : \bar{y}, \quad (27)$$

$$\mathbf{j} = \mathcal{P}^+ : \mathbf{j}^+ + \zeta \mathcal{P}^- : \mathbf{j}^-, \quad \mathcal{J} = \mathcal{P}^+ : \mathcal{J}^+ : \mathcal{P}^+ + \zeta^2 \mathcal{P}^- : \mathcal{J}^- : \mathcal{P}^-, \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{k}^+ = \zeta \mathbf{k}^-, \quad \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B}^+ = \zeta \mathbf{B}^-, \quad (29)$$

so that Eq. (26) is equivalent to Eq. (19) in entire tension/compression.

Substituting Eq. (26) into Eq. (10) gives

$$\dot{\mathbf{d}} = \dot{\lambda} \mathbf{n} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{\beta} = \dot{\lambda}, \quad (30)$$

where $\mathbf{n} = \partial f / \partial \bar{y} = \partial \bar{y}_{eq} / \partial \bar{y}$ denotes the normal to the damage surface. Taking time derivatives on both sides of Eq. (26) gives the consistency condition as

$$\dot{f} = \dot{y}_{eq} - \frac{dB}{d\beta} \dot{\beta} = 0, \quad (31)$$

from which the governing equations of damage evolution can be derived. According to Zhang and Yu [37],

$$\dot{\mathcal{P}}_{mnpq}^- \equiv \mathcal{Q}_{mnklpq}^- \dot{\epsilon}_{kl}. \quad (32)$$

\dot{y}_{eq} can be obtained through some derivation as

$$\dot{y}_{eq} = \mathbf{n} : \dot{\bar{y}} - \boldsymbol{\kappa} : \dot{\epsilon}, \quad (33)$$

where

$$\mathbf{n} = (1 - \chi) \frac{\mathcal{J} : \bar{y}}{\|\bar{y}\|_{\mathcal{J}}} + \chi \mathbf{j}, \quad (34)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_{ij} = & \frac{1 - \chi}{2 \|\bar{y}\|_{\mathcal{J}}} \bar{y}_{kl} \left[\mathcal{Q}_{klijpq}^- \left(\mathcal{J}_{pqrs}^+ \mathcal{P}_{rsmn}^+ - \zeta^2 \mathcal{J}_{pqrs}^- \mathcal{P}_{rsmn}^- \right) \right. \\ & \left. + \left(\mathcal{P}_{klpq}^+ \mathcal{J}_{pqrs}^+ - \zeta^2 \mathcal{P}_{klpq}^- \mathcal{J}_{pqrs}^- \right) \mathcal{Q}_{rsijmn}^- \right] \bar{y}_{mn} + \chi \mathcal{Q}_{klijmn}^- (j_{mn}^+ - \zeta j_{mn}^-). \end{aligned} \quad (34')$$

More details on the derivation of Eqs. (32)–(34) can be found in Zhang and Yu [37]. Substituting Eq. (33) into Eq. (31) and rearranging the equation give

$$\dot{\beta} = \dot{\lambda} = \frac{\mathbf{n} : \dot{\bar{y}} - \boldsymbol{\kappa} : \dot{\epsilon}}{\frac{dB}{d\beta}}. \quad (35)$$

Substituting Eq. (35) into the first equation of Eq. (30) gives

$$\dot{\mathbf{d}} = \frac{\mathbf{n} : \dot{\bar{y}} - \boldsymbol{\kappa} : \dot{\epsilon}}{\frac{dB}{d\beta}} \mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n}}{\frac{dB}{d\beta}} : \dot{\bar{y}} - \frac{\mathbf{n} \otimes \boldsymbol{\kappa}}{\frac{dB}{d\beta}} : \dot{\epsilon} \equiv \mathcal{S} : \dot{\bar{y}} - \mathcal{R} : \dot{\epsilon}, \quad (36)$$

which is the governing equation of damage evolution. $-\boldsymbol{\kappa} : \dot{\epsilon}$ in Eq. (35) (or $-\mathcal{R} : \dot{\epsilon}$ in Eq. (36)) can be nonzero when the principal stress axes rotate in combined tension–compression. $\boldsymbol{\kappa} : \dot{\epsilon}$ can be so great that it makes $\dot{\lambda}$ negative. In this case, loading/unloading conditions Eq. (11) is not satisfied, and damages neither initiate nor evolve.

The key point of modeling damage deactivation is to distinguish between tensile and compressive damages. Substituting Eq. (28) into Eq. (34) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{n} = & \left[(1 - \chi) \frac{\mathcal{P}^+ : \mathcal{J}^+ : \mathcal{P}^+ : \bar{y}}{\|\bar{y}\|_{\mathcal{J}}} + \chi \mathcal{P}^+ : \mathbf{j}^+ \right] \\ & + \left[(1 - \chi) \frac{\zeta^2 \mathcal{P}^- : \mathcal{J}^- : \mathcal{P}^- : \bar{y}}{\|\bar{y}\|_{\mathcal{J}}} + \chi \zeta \mathcal{P}^- : \mathbf{j}^- \right] \equiv (\mathbf{n})^+ + (\mathbf{n})^-. \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

where $(\mathbf{n})^\pm$ denotes the projection of \mathbf{n} onto σ^\pm . Substituting Eq. (37) into the first equation of Eq. (30) gives

$$\dot{\mathbf{d}} = \dot{\lambda} (\mathbf{n})^+ + \dot{\lambda} (\mathbf{n})^- \equiv \dot{\mathbf{d}}^+ + \dot{\mathbf{d}}^-, \quad (38)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{d}}^+$ and $\dot{\mathbf{d}}^-$ denote the tensile and compressive parts of $\dot{\mathbf{d}}$, respectively. The tensile and compressive parts of \mathbf{d} can then be obtained as

$$\mathbf{d}^+ = \int_0^t \dot{\mathbf{d}}^+ dt \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{d}^- = \mathbf{d} - \mathbf{d}^+, \quad (39)$$

respectively. Following Chaboche [12], assume that: 1. a constant portion of tensile damages are inactive in compression; 2. all compressive damages are active all the time. Let $\eta\mathbf{d}^+$ denote the portion of \mathbf{d}^+ remaining active in compression so that

$$\mathbf{d}^* (\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}^+) = \mathbf{d} - (1 - \eta) \mathcal{P}^- : \mathbf{d}^+, \quad (40)$$

namely the nominal second-order damage tensor, measuring active damages. Eqs. (2), (3), and (14) can then be amended as

$$\psi_e = \psi_e(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \mathbf{d}^*), \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \rho \left(\frac{\partial \psi_e}{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}} \right)_{\mathbf{d}^*}, \quad \mathbf{y} = -\rho \left(\frac{\partial \psi_e}{\partial \mathbf{d}^*} \right)_{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}, \quad (41)$$

$$\mathcal{D} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 d_{ij}^* \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_j \otimes \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_j, \quad (42)$$

respectively. In fact, in Eqs. (40)–(42), \mathbf{d}^* serves as a pseudo-state variable, and \mathbf{d} a variable of \mathbf{d}^* .

4. EXPLICIT INTEGRATION SCHEME

The finite element implementation of a nonlocal model has been extensively studied (see Peerlings et al. [27], Borino et al. [9], Desmorat et al. [18], and Poh and Swaddiwudhipong [29] for examples). A nonlocal model can be implemented in commercial finite element code Abaqus/Explicit via VUMAT, for structural analysis, where:

1. Abaqus/Explicit can be used to solve complicated quasi-static problems;
2. VUMAT is used to define the constitutive behavior of a material [32].

Let $(\cdot)_n$ denote a quantity at the end of the n th time increment, which is t_n . When calling VUMAT at an integration point, Abaqus/Explicit passes in $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n$ and $\Delta\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ and gets back $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}$, where $\Delta(\cdot)$ denotes the increment in a quantity over time interval $[t_n, t_{n+1}]$. Note that an increment in a quantity can be related to the rate of this quantity using the Euler method (e.g. $\Delta\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}\Delta t$). Suppose that all the state variables at t_n , as well as $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$, are known. The task is to find the other rates of state variables.

It is beneficial to find the relationship between $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ and $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$. Taking time derivatives on both sides of the first equation of Eq. (17) gives

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = \dot{\mathcal{M}}^{-1} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}. \quad (43)$$

Firstly $\dot{\mathcal{M}}^{-1}$ awaits determination. Taking time derivatives on both sides of Eq. (15) gives $\dot{\mathcal{M}}^{-1} = -\dot{\mathcal{D}}$, where $\dot{\mathcal{D}}$ can be obtained through some derivation as [37]

$$\dot{\mathcal{D}}_{ijmn} = \mathcal{I}_{ijklmn} \dot{d}_{kl} - (1 - \eta) \mathcal{I}_{ijpqmn} \mathcal{D}_{pqklrs}^- d_{rs}^+ \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{kl} \equiv \mathcal{I}_{ijklmn} \dot{d}_{kl} - \mathcal{R}_{ijklmn} \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{kl}, \quad (44)$$

where

$$\mathcal{I} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_j \otimes \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_j \otimes \mathbf{e}_i \otimes \mathbf{e}_j. \quad (45)$$

$-\mathcal{R}_{ijklmn} \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{kl}$ in Eq. (44) is nonzero when some active/inactive damages become inactive/active due to the rotation of the principal stress axes. Noting that, in Eq. (44), $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{d}}$ can be arbitrarily chosen, gives $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{D}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}, \mathbf{d})$ (or $\mathcal{M}^{-1} = \mathcal{M}^{-1}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}, \mathbf{d})$) and

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{D}_{ijmn}}{\partial d_{kl}} = -\frac{\partial \mathcal{M}_{ijmn}^{-1}}{\partial d_{kl}} = \mathcal{I}_{ijklmn} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{D}_{ijmn}}{\partial \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{kl}} = -\frac{\partial \mathcal{M}_{ijmn}^{-1}}{\partial \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}_{kl}} = -\mathcal{R}_{ijklmn}. \quad (46)$$

The first term on the right side of Eq. (43) can then be expressed as

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{ijmn}^{-1} \epsilon_{mn} = -\mathcal{I}_{ijklmn} \epsilon_{mn} \dot{d}_{kl} + \mathcal{R}_{ijklmn} \epsilon_{mn} \dot{\tilde{\epsilon}}_{kl}. \quad (47)$$

Substituting Eq. (47) into Eq. (43) gives

$$(\mathcal{I} - \mathcal{R} : \epsilon) : \dot{\tilde{\epsilon}} = -(\mathcal{I} : \epsilon) : \dot{d} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \dot{\epsilon}. \quad (48)$$

Eq. (48) leads one to find the relationship between \dot{d} and $\dot{\epsilon}$. Recall that

$$\rho \psi_e(\epsilon, d^*) = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon : \mathcal{C} : \epsilon = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon : (\mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1}) : \epsilon. \quad (49)$$

Substituting Eq. (49) into the third equation of Eq. (41) gives

$$\mathbf{y} = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\epsilon} : \mathcal{M} : (\mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I}) : \mathcal{M} : \tilde{\epsilon}, \quad (50)$$

which indicates that $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{y}(\tilde{\epsilon}, d)$ and that

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \tilde{\epsilon}} : \dot{\tilde{\epsilon}} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial d} : \dot{d}. \quad (51)$$

The partial derivatives in Eq. (51) await determination. Note that $\mathcal{M} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} = \mathcal{I}$. Taking time derivatives on both sides gives

$$\dot{\mathcal{M}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} = -\mathcal{M} : \dot{\mathcal{M}}^{-1} \quad \text{or} \quad \dot{\mathcal{M}} = -\mathcal{M} : \dot{\mathcal{M}}^{-1} : \mathcal{M}. \quad (52)$$

Combining Eqs. (46) and (52) gives

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{M}_{ijmn}}{\partial d_{kl}} = \mathcal{M}_{ijpq} \mathcal{I}_{pqklrs} \mathcal{M}_{rsmn} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{M}_{ijmn}}{\partial \tilde{\epsilon}_{kl}} = -\mathcal{M}_{ijpq} \mathcal{R}_{pqklrs} \mathcal{M}_{rsmn}. \quad (53)$$

The partial derivatives can then be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \tilde{\epsilon}} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathcal{M} : (\mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I}) : \mathcal{M} : \tilde{\epsilon} + \tilde{\epsilon} : \mathcal{M} : (\mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I}) : \mathcal{M} \right] \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\epsilon} : \left[-\mathcal{M} : \mathcal{R} : \mathcal{M} : (\mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I}) : \mathcal{M} \right. \\ &\left. + \mathcal{M} : (\mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{R} + \mathcal{R} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I}) : \mathcal{M} - \mathcal{M} : (\mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I}) : \mathcal{M} : \mathcal{R} : \mathcal{M} \right] : \tilde{\epsilon}, \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial d} &= \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\epsilon} : \left[\mathcal{M} : \mathcal{I} : \mathcal{M} : (\mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I}) : \mathcal{M} \right. \\ &\left. - 2\mathcal{M} : \mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I} : \mathcal{M} + \mathcal{M} : (\mathcal{I} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{M}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \tilde{\mathcal{C}} : \mathcal{I}) : \mathcal{M} : \mathcal{I} : \mathcal{M} \right] : \tilde{\epsilon}. \end{aligned} \quad (54')$$

Substituting Eq. (36) into Eq. (48) gives

$$[\mathcal{I} - \mathcal{R} : \epsilon - (\mathcal{I} : \epsilon) : \mathcal{R}] : \dot{\tilde{\epsilon}} = -(\mathcal{I} : \epsilon) : \mathcal{S} : \dot{\mathbf{y}} + \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \dot{\epsilon}. \quad (55)$$

Let

$$\mathcal{I}^* = [\mathcal{I} - \mathcal{R} : \epsilon - (\mathcal{I} : \epsilon) : \mathcal{R}]^{-1}. \quad (56)$$

Substituting Eq. (56) into Eq. (55) and rearranging the equation give

$$\dot{\tilde{\epsilon}} = -\mathcal{I}^* : (\mathcal{I} : \epsilon) : \mathcal{S} : \dot{\mathbf{y}} + \mathcal{I}^* : \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \dot{\epsilon}. \quad (57)$$

Substituting Eq. (57) into Eq. (36) gives

$$\dot{d} = [\mathcal{I} + \mathcal{R} : \mathcal{I}^* : (\mathcal{I} : \epsilon)] : \mathcal{S} : \dot{\mathbf{y}} - \mathcal{R} : \mathcal{I}^* : \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \dot{\epsilon} \quad (58)$$

Substituting Eqs. (57) and (58) into Eqs. (51) gives

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}} = \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \tilde{\epsilon}} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial d} : \mathcal{R} \right) : \mathcal{I}^* : \mathcal{M}^{-1} : \dot{\tilde{\epsilon}} + \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial d} - \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \tilde{\epsilon}} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial d} : \mathcal{R} \right) : \mathcal{I}^* : (\mathcal{I} : \epsilon) \right] : \mathcal{S} : \dot{\mathbf{y}}. \quad (59)$$

Substituting Eq. (59) into Eqs. (6) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}) &= \int_{\Omega} \bar{w}(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\xi}) \left[\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{d}} : \mathcal{R} \right) : \mathcal{I}^* : \mathcal{M}^{-1} \right] (\boldsymbol{\xi}) : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi} \\ &+ \int_{\Omega} \bar{w}(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\xi}) \left\{ \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{d}} - \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{d}} : \mathcal{R} \right) : \mathcal{I}^* : (\mathcal{J} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}) \right] : \mathcal{S} \right\} (\boldsymbol{\xi}) : \dot{\mathbf{y}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi}. \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

Let

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}_0(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\Omega} \bar{w}(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\xi}) \left[\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{d}} : \mathcal{R} \right) : \mathcal{I}^* : \mathcal{M}^{-1} \right] (\boldsymbol{\xi}) : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad (61)$$

$$\mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) = \bar{w}(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\xi}) \left\{ \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{d}} - \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{d}} : \mathcal{R} \right) : \mathcal{I}^* : (\mathcal{J} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}) \right] : \mathcal{S} \right\} (\boldsymbol{\xi}). \quad (61')$$

Substituting Eq. (61) into Eq. (60) gives

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}) = \dot{\mathbf{y}}_0(\mathbf{x}) + \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) : \dot{\mathbf{y}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad (62)$$

which is a Fredholm integral equation of the second kind. Eq. (62) can be solved by iteratively finding $\dot{\mathbf{y}}_i$'s ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}_1(\mathbf{x}) = \dot{\mathbf{y}}_0(\mathbf{x}) + \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) : \dot{\mathbf{y}}_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi} \quad (63)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}_2(\mathbf{x}) = \dot{\mathbf{y}}_0(\mathbf{x}) + \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) : \dot{\mathbf{y}}_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi} \quad (63')$$

...

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}_n(\mathbf{x}) = \dot{\mathbf{y}}_0(\mathbf{x}) + \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\xi}) : \dot{\mathbf{y}}_{n-1}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi} \quad (63'')$$

The Neumann series solution is then

$$\dot{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \dot{\mathbf{y}}_n(\mathbf{x}), \quad (64)$$

from which $\dot{\mathbf{y}}$ can be computed. According to numerical experiments, it generally takes 11 to 15 iterations for Eq. (64) to converge (i.e., $11 < n < 15$). After having reached convergence, substituting $\dot{\mathbf{y}}$ and $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ into Eqs. (57) and (58) gives $\dot{\mathbf{d}}$ and $\dot{\bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}}$.

$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ still awaits determination. Taking time derivatives on both sides of the first equation of Eq. (16) gives

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \dot{\mathbf{C}} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} + \mathbf{C} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}. \quad (65)$$

The first term on the right side of Eq. (65) can be further expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{ijrs} \epsilon_{rs} &= \left(\dot{\mathcal{M}}_{ijmn}^{-1} \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{mnpq} \mathcal{M}_{pqrs}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}_{ijmn}^{-1} \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{mnpq} \dot{\mathcal{M}}_{pqrs}^{-1} \right) \epsilon_{rs} \\ &= - \left[\left(\mathcal{J}_{ijklmn} \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{mnpq} \mathcal{M}_{pqrs}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}_{ijmn}^{-1} \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{mnpq} \mathcal{J}_{pqklrs} \right) \epsilon_{rs} \right] \dot{d}_{kl} \\ &\quad + \left[\left(\mathcal{R}_{ijklmn} \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{mnpq} \mathcal{M}_{pqrs}^{-1} + \mathcal{M}_{ijmn}^{-1} \tilde{\mathcal{C}}_{mnpq} \mathcal{R}_{pqklrs} \right) \epsilon_{rs} \right] \dot{\bar{\epsilon}}_{kl} \\ &\equiv - \left(\mathcal{F}_{ijklrs} \epsilon_{rs} \right) \dot{d}_{kl} + \left(\mathcal{G}_{ijklrs} \epsilon_{rs} \right) \dot{\bar{\epsilon}}_{kl}. \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

Combining Eqs. (58)–(66) gives

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = - \left(\mathcal{F} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \right) : \dot{\mathbf{d}} + \left(\mathcal{G} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \right) : \dot{\bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}} + \mathbf{C} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}. \quad (67)$$

Since $\dot{\mathbf{d}}$, $\dot{\bar{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}}$, and $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ are all known at the current stage, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ can be uniquely determined from Eq. (67). Till now, all rates of state variables necessary for updating state variables. In this paper, the present explicit integration scheme is implemented in a Euler–Trapezoidal predictor–corrector method to achieve second-order accuracy.

5. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Le Bellego et al. [24] performed a series of SENB tests on concrete beams having different dimensions,

Figure 1: SENB specimen.

Figure 2: Finite element model.

measured the load–deflection curve during each test, and calibrated the material parameters associated with their nonlocal model. In this section, the present model will be validated through calibrating its associated material parameters from these experimental data.

Figure 1 depicts the experimental setting of the test on the smallest SENB specimen, which has a half length of 120 mm, a height of 80 mm, and a width of 40 mm (not shown), a edge notch length of 8 mm. A commercial finite element code, Abaqus/Explicit, is used to simulate the tests, and the present model is implemented in Abaqus/Explicit via user subroutine VUMAT. Noting the beam width is much smaller than the beam length and that the two end faces normal to the beam width direction are traction free, assume that plane stress conditions prevail over the beam. Noting that the geometry and the loads are both symmetric to the vertical axis of symmetry of the specimen, only consider the left half of the geometry for efficiency purposes. Figure 2 depicts the finite element model of this specimen. The 2D finite element model is meshed with 2576 plane stress elements with reduced integration (CPS4R for rectangular elements and CPS3 for triangular elements). The region surrounding a potential crack is found to be well resolved, and the finite element model is found to be capable of producing converged results.

Experimental observations indicate that the degradation of a specimen was due to tensile damages. To facilitate the calibration, assume that the concrete exhibits full damage deactivation ($\eta = 0$) and no compressive damage initiation and evolution ($\zeta = 0$). Due to the absence of necessary experimental data (e.g., those from uniaxial and biaxial tests), assume that the concrete exhibits elastic isotropy, like most other concrete, and set $\chi = 0.5$ and $j_{ij} = 1$ for demonstration purposes (see Abu Al-Rub and Kim [1] for similar treatments). Numerical experiments indicate that the concrete has a \tilde{E} of 38.5 GPa, $\tilde{\nu}$ of 0.24, a ultimate tensile strength of 1.5 MPa, and a k_d of 2.6×10^{-5} MPa. The task is to determine the damage accumulation law, $B(\beta)$. Numerical experiments indicate that an exponential damage accumulation law,

$$B(\beta) = Q [\exp(b\beta) - 1], \quad (68)$$

makes the predictions have good fits to the experimental data, where Q and b are two positive damage accumulation parameters. The fitted parameters are hereby Q , b , and l_c (the characteristic length).

The calibration process involves iteratively adjusting Q , b , and l_c and finding the values of Q , b , and l_c

Table 1: Fitted parameters of a type of concrete.

Q (MPa)	b	l_c (mm)
1.235×10^{-5}	7.5	2.0

making the predictions have the best fit to the experimental data. Table 1 lists the fitted parameters. Figure 4: Case 1 shows the the experimental and the fitted load–deflection curves. It can be seen that the prediction fit the experimental data well. To further validate the present model, hold Q , b , and l_c fixed (because they are material parameters independent of specimen dimensions), and consider another specimen in Le Bellego et al. [24], whose dimensions except width are twice of the corresponding dimensions of the smallest specimen. Figure 4: Case 2 shows the the experimental and the predicted load–deflection curves for this specimen. It can be seen that the prediction still fit the experimental data well. Meanwhile, it is worth notice that the predictions for Cases 1 and 2 are not similar but exhibit distinct trends. This indicates that size effects do exist in real materials, such as concrete. This finding is in agreement with experimental observations. All these indicate that the present model can produce realistic fracture paths and capture size effects in real materials.

Figure 3: Experimental and predicted load–deflection curves for different specimens.

Figure 4: Load–deflection curves for different values of l_c .

It is beneficial to investigate how l_c affects the load–deflection curves. Figure 3 shows the load–deflection curves for different values of l_c , where Q and b are held fixed. It can be seen that, as l_c increases, the load reaches a higher peak value at a larger deflection and more rapid drops afterwards. In fact, l_c directly determines the width of a strain localization band due to fracture: a low value of l_c leads to a narrow band, and a high value a wide band. On one hand, creating a wide band needs more work to be done and requires a high load; on the other hand, the growth of a wide band tends to be unstable and may cause a sudden drop in the load. Figure 3 again indicates the significance and necessity of calibrating l_c via experiments.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a nonlocal continuum damage model for brittle fracture is developed based on a recently developed “local” model, with an integral-type regularization technique, so that it can rigorously handle damage anisotropy, distinct tensile and compressive damage behavior, and damage deactivation. The “local” damage conjugate force tensor is regularized to yield a nonlocal one, and the thermodynamic equations are formulated in a nonlocally generalized standard manner. A fully explicit integration scheme for the present model is developed.

The following findings can be obtained from the results:

1. the present model is found to be capable of producing realistic fracture paths and capturing size effects in real materials;

2. the characteristic length of material heterogeneity is found to significantly affect a load–deflection curve and should be calibrated via experiments.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above findings:

1. the present model can be incorporated into a multiscale modeling approach (e.g., the mechanics of structure genome [36]) for fracture prediction in composites;
2. a wide variety of mechanical behavior can be incorporated into the present model in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abu Al-Rub, R.K., Kim, S.M., 2010. Computational applications of a coupled plasticity-damage constitutive model for simulating plain concrete fracture. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 77, 1577–1603.
- [2] Abu Al-Rub, R.K., Voyiadjis, G.Z., 2009. Gradient-enhanced coupled plasticity-anisotropic damage model for concrete fracture: computational aspects and applications. *International Journal of Damage Mechanics* 18, 115–154.
- [3] Bažant, Z.P., 1976. Instability, ductility, and size effect in strain-softening concrete. *Journal of the Engineering Mechanics Division* 102, 331–344.
- [4] Bažant, Z.P., Jirásek, M., 2002. Nonlocal integral formulations of plasticity and damage: survey of progress. *Journal of Engineering Mechanics* 128, 1119–1149.
- [5] Bažant, Z.P., Pijaudier-Cabot, G., 1989. Measurement of characteristic length of nonlocal continuum. *Journal of Engineering Mechanics* 115, 755–767.
- [6] Besson, J., Cailletaud, G., Chaboche, J.L., Forest, S., 2009. Non-linear mechanics of materials. volume 167 of *Solid Mechanics and Its Applications*. Springer, New York.
- [7] Betten, J., 1983. Damage tensors in continuum mechanics. *Journal de Mecanique Theorique et Appliquee* 2, 13–32.
- [8] Betten, J., 2001. Mathematical modelling of materials behavior under creep conditions. *Applied Mechanics Reviews* 54, 107–132.
- [9] Borino, G., Failla, B., Parrinello, F., 2003. A symmetric nonlocal damage theory. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 40, 3621–3645.
- [10] Borino, G., Fuschi, P., Polizzotto, C., 1999. A thermodynamic approach to nonlocal plasticity and related variational principles. *Journal of Applied Mechanics* 66, 952–963.
- [11] Chaboche, J.L., 1992. Damage induced anisotropy: on the difficulties associated with the active/passive unilateral condition. *International Journal of Damage Mechanics* 1, 148–171.
- [12] Chaboche, J.L., 1993. Development of continuum damage mechanics for elastic solids sustaining anisotropic and unilateral damage. *International Journal of Damage Mechanics* 2, 311–329.
- [13] Chaboche, J.L., Lesne, P.M., Maire, J.F., 1995. Continuum damage mechanics, anisotropy and damage deactivation for brittle materials like concrete and ceramic composites. *International Journal of Damage Mechanics* 4, 5–22.
- [14] Chaboche, J.L., Maire, J.F., 2002. A new micromechanics based cdm model and its application to cmc's. *Aerospace Science and Technology* 6, 131–145.
- [15] Cicekli, U., Voyiadjis, G.Z., Abu Al-Rub, R.K., 2007. A plasticity and anisotropic damage model for plain concrete. *International Journal of Plasticity* 23, 1874–1900.
- [16] Comi, C., Perego, U., 2001. Numerical aspects of nonlocal damage analyses. *Revue européenne des éléments finis* 10, 227–242.

- [17] Cordebois, J.P., Sidoroff, F., 1979. Anisotropie élastique induite par endommagement. *Comportement Mécanique des Solides Anisotropes* , 761–774.
- [18] Desmorat, R., Gatuingt, F., Ragueneau, F., 2007. Nonlocal anisotropic damage model and related computational aspects for quasi-brittle materials. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 74, 1539–1560.
- [19] Faria, R., Oliver, J., Cervera, M., 1998. A strain-based plastic viscous-damage model for massive concrete structures. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 35, 1533–1558.
- [20] Hackl, K., 1997. Generalized standard media and variational principles in classical and finite strain elastoplasticity. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids* 45, 667–688.
- [21] Halphen, B., Nguyen, Q.S., 1975. Sur les matériaux standard généralisés. *Journal de Mécanique* 14, 39–63.
- [22] Ju, J.W., 1989. On energy-based coupled elastoplastic damage theories: constitutive modeling and computational aspects. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 25, 803–833.
- [23] Ladevèze, P., Lemaitre, J., 1984. Damage effective stress in quasi unilateral conditions, in: 16th International Congress of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics, Lyngby, Denmark.
- [24] Le Bellego, C., Gérard, B., Pijaudier-Cabot, G., 2000. Chemo-mechanical effects in mortar beams subjected to water hydrolysis. *Journal of Engineering Mechanics* 126, 266–272.
- [25] Lorentz, E., Andrieux, S., 2003. Analysis of non-local models through energetic formulations. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 40, 2905–2936.
- [26] Ortiz, M., 1985. A constitutive theory for the inelastic behavior of concrete. *Mechanics of Materials* 4, 67–93.
- [27] Peerlings, R.H.J., De Borst, R., Brekelmans, W.A.M., De Vree, J.H.P., 1996. Gradient enhanced damage for quasi-brittle materials. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 39, 3391–3403.
- [28] Pijaudier-Cabot, G., Bažant, Z.P., 1987. Nonlocal damage theory. *Journal of Engineering Mechanics* 113, 1512–1533.
- [29] Poh, L.H., Swaddiwudhipong, S., 2009. Over-nonlocal gradient enhanced plastic-damage model for concrete. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 46, 4369–4378.
- [30] Ramtani, S., 1990. Contribution à la modélisation du comportement multiaxial du béton endommagé avec description du caractère unilatéral. Ph.D. thesis. Paris 6.
- [31] Simo, J.C., Hughes, T.J.R., 1998. Computational inelasticity. volume 7 of *Interdisciplinary Applied Mathematics*. Springer, New York.
- [32] Simulia, 2013. Abaqus 6.13 documentation.
- [33] Voyiadjis, G.Z., Taqieddin, Z.N., Kattan, P.I., 2008. Anisotropic damage–plasticity model for concrete. *International Journal of Plasticity* 24, 1946–1965.
- [34] Voyiadjis, G.Z., Taqieddin, Z.N., Kattan, P.I., 2009. Theoretical formulation of a coupled elastic–plastic anisotropic damage model for concrete using the strain energy equivalence concept. *International Journal of Damage Mechanics* 18, 603–638.
- [35] Wu, J.Y., Li, J., Faria, R., 2006. An energy release rate-based plastic-damage model for concrete. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 43, 583–612.
- [36] Yu, W., 2016. A unified theory for constitutive modeling of composites. *Journal of Mechanics of Materials and Structures* 11, 379–411.
- [37] Zhang, L., Yu, W., 2017. Constitutive modeling of damageable brittle and quasi-brittle materials. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* .